

Atomic Autoresearch: Autonomous Hyperparameter Optimization in a Browser-Based Scalar Autograd Transformer

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Abstract — This work ports Karpathy's autoresearch framework to a dependency-free, browser-executable implementation: a single 38 KB HTML file containing a complete GPT transformer, scalar autograd engine, Adam optimizer, evaluation harness, and autonomous experiment controller. The system implements architectural features from the original H100-scale codebase — Rotary Position Embeddings (RoPE), ReluSquared activations, value embeddings with gated mixing, logit soft-capping, and residual skip connections — each as a toggleable feature the search can enable or disable. Evaluation spans seven character-level sequence domains: English names (32K and 200 documents), antimicrobial peptides, SMILES molecular notation, startup company names, dinosaur names, and cocktail names. The autonomous loop discovers domain-dependent architectural preferences: data-rich domains benefit from feature additions, while data-poor domains benefit primarily from learning rate tuning. RoPE emerges as the most broadly beneficial feature (kept in 4 of 7 domains). Improvements range from 0.2% to 41.7% BPB reduction, achieved through up to 19 automated experiments per domain with zero human intervention. The system (and repository code) executes in any modern browser on commodity hardware with no perceptible lag, demonstrating that the autoresearch paradigm remains viable at the absolute minimum scale.

Index Terms — autonomous machine learning, neural architecture search, scalar automatic differentiation, character-level language modeling, browser-based deep learning, domain-dependent hyperparameter optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

Karpathy's *autoresearch*^[1] demonstrated that neural network research can be automated: an AI agent modifies a training script, trains for a fixed time budget on an H100 GPU, evaluates via bits-per-byte (BPB), keeps improvements, discards regressions, and repeats up to 100 experiments overnight. The original system trains 50M+ parameter models using PyTorch, Flash Attention 3^[5], and a Muon optimizer^[6] with Newton-Schulz orthogonalization on the ClimbMix-400B dataset.

This paper asks: *what is the most atomic form of this idea?* Karpathy's earlier work established that a complete GPT can be expressed in ~150 lines of dependency-free Python^{[7][8]}, with every operation traced through a scalar Value class. *Can the autoresearch loop fit in this same atomic format, running in a web browser?*

The answer is yes. Rather than merely confirming that *autoresearch* works at small scale, cross-domain evaluation reveals that the optimal architecture is domain-dependent. The autonomous search discovers different feature sets for different sequence types: data-rich domains absorb more architectural complexity, while data-poor domains prefer simpler models with tuned optimization.

Contributions: (1) a JavaScript port of every architectural feature from *train.py* into scalar autograd, running as a single HTML file; (2) an autonomous experiment protocol with learning rate auto-scaling; and (3) empirical results across seven domains showing domain-dependent preferences discovered without human guidance.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Pedagogical Implementations

This work follows a lineage of pedagogical implementations. Karpathy's *micrograd*^[7] demonstrated reverse-mode automatic differentiation in ~100 lines of Python. His atomic GPT^[8] extended this to a complete transformer. The JavaScript port preserves scalar-by-scalar clarity while adding `tanh` for logit soft-capping and `sigmoid` for value embedding gates. The browser environment adds accessibility — no Python, PyTorch, or GPU drivers required.

B. Transformer Architecture Components

Features in the search space come from recent research. RoPE^[2] encodes position through query/key rotation. ReluSquared^[3] was discovered by the Primer search. Value embeddings follow ResFormer^[4]. Logit soft-capping via `tanh` from Gemma 2^[9] prevents extreme logit values. RMSNorm^[10] replaces LayerNorm throughout. Each is implemented as a Boolean toggle.

C. Neural Architecture Search

The approach relates to NAS^[11] but operates as automated ablation. The system tests named features against a running best — more analogous to ablation tables than to RL-based NAS. The fixed-compute-budget protocol follows *autoresearch*^[1]: experiments are compared by metric within a fixed step count. The scoring resembles building blocks in genetic programming more than classic high-dimensional optimization.

D. Optimizer Considerations

The full *autoresearch* uses Muon^[6] (Newton-Schulz polar orthogonalization) for matrix parameters and AdamW^[12] for embeddings. The browser implementation uses AdamW throughout, compensating with learning rate auto-scaling: LR proportional to $1/\sqrt{\text{n_embd}/16}$.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

A. Implementation

The complete system is a single HTML file (38 KB) containing: (a) a JavaScript Value class with topological-sort backpropagation; (b) a GPT decoder with configurable features; (c) Adam with bias correction ($\text{beta1}=0.85$, $\text{beta2}=0.99$); (d) BPB evaluation; (e) autonomous experiment loop with model snapshotting; and (f) a visualization dashboard with live loss curves, weight heatmaps, attention patterns, architecture flow diagrams, and side-by-side generation comparison.

B. Baseline Architecture

The baseline: 1-layer transformer, 16-dimensional embeddings, 4 attention heads, 16-token context, absolute position embeddings, ReLU, RMSNorm, no biases ($\sim 4,200$ parameters). The autoresearch loop adds features *on top of* this baseline. A critical design lesson: starting with all features enabled and removing them proved far less effective than starting simple and adding incrementally.

C. Autoresearch Protocol and BPB Metric

The protocol: (1) train baseline, evaluate BPB, snapshot; (2) for each mutation, apply to current best, train fresh, evaluate; (3) if BPB improves, keep and snapshot; otherwise revert; (4) restore best model after all experiments. The mutation pool includes LR multipliers ($0.3x-4x$), feature additions (+RoPE, +ReluSquared, +softcap, +x0 skip, +VE), architectural changes (depth 2, widen, block size), and one compound mutation (depth 2 + widen 24). **Learning rate auto-scaling** multiplies effective LR by $\sqrt{16/\text{n_embd}}$ when width changes.

The evaluation metric is bits per byte (BPB): the sum of per-token cross-entropy losses, divided by total UTF-8 byte count, scaled by $1/\ln(2)$ to convert to bits. BPB is vocabulary-independent, provides an information-theoretic baseline (8.0 = no compression; English text $\sim 1.0-1.5$), and matches the metric used by the original *autoresearch*^[1], enabling cross-scale comparison.

The evaluation metric is bits per byte (BPB): the total cross-entropy loss over all target tokens, divided by the total byte length of those targets, converted to bits. BPB offers three properties critical to the *autoresearch* setting. First, it is vocabulary-independent because the denominator counts raw UTF-8 bytes rather than tokens, BPB remains comparable across configurations that might alter the effective vocabulary through tokenization changes or special token handling. This matters when the autonomous loop tests mutations that change model capacity or context length, which can shift the implicit token-to-byte ratio. Second, BPB provides an information-theoretic baseline: a value of 8.0 corresponds to no compression (one bit per bit of input), while the entropy of English text sits

near 1.0–1.5 BPB, giving both an upper bound and a meaningful floor. Third, BPB is the metric used by the original *autoresearch* framework [1], making cross-scale comparison between the H100 results (~ 0.977 BPB on web text) and the atomic results (2.3–6.2 BPB on character-level domains) interpretable on the same axis — the gap reflects data and model scale, not a difference in measurement.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Domains

Seven character-level sequence domains spanning a range of alphabet sizes, sequence lengths, and structural properties: Baby Names (32K) — 32,033 names, 27 tokens; Baby Names (200) — 200 embedded names; Antimicrobial Peptides (AMP) — 44 real AMPs, 20 amino acid tokens; SMILES Molecules — 36 small molecules, 18 tokens; Startup Names — 45 tech companies, 41 tokens; Dinosaur Names — 25 genera, 34 tokens; Cocktail Names — 15 classics, 32 tokens.

B. Results Summary

Table I summarizes verified results. Each domain ran 17–19 experiments with 850 training steps at base LR 0.032.

TABLE I. Cross-domain autoresearch results

Domain	Docs	Base	Best	$\Delta\%$	Kept	Key Features
Names 32K	32K	3.79	3.78	0.2	4/17	config tuning
Names 200	200	3.63	3.46	4.9	4/17	RoPE+softcap+VE
Peptides	44	3.72	2.72	26.9	8/17	all features
SMILES	36	2.13	1.69	20.7	5/19	LR+RoPE+ReluSq
Startups	45	5.58	5.44	2.5	2/19	block_size 24
Dinosaurs	25	6.05	3.53	41.7	3/19	LR 2x+depth 2
Cocktails	15	10.16	8.18	19.5	5/19	LR+RoPE+VE

C. Cross-Domain Feature Preferences

RoPE is the most universal feature — kept in 4 of 7 domains (Names 200, Peptides, SMILES, Cocktails). Positional encoding via rotation benefits diverse sequence types regardless of alphabet or data size.

Peptides absorb the most features — 8 of 17 experiments kept (26.9% improvement). Every major feature contributed: LR tuning \rightarrow RoPE \rightarrow ReluSquared \rightarrow x0 skip \rightarrow value embeddings \rightarrow depth 2. The 20-character amino acid alphabet has rich compositional structure that rewards architectural complexity.

Dinosaurs show BPB-quality divergence — 41.7% BPB improvement (largest of any domain) but the baseline produced 7/10 verified real dinosaur names while the best model generates garbled fragments. The metric improved because probability is distributed more evenly, but memorized recall degraded. This is a genuine methodological finding about BPB as a quality proxy.

Softcap helps only Names 200 — a clean result that logit soft-capping^[9] benefits small-data regimes where training

instability matters more, but adds unnecessary nonlinearity at 4,200 parameters with abundant data.

Startups and Names 32K show near-zero improvement (2.5% and 0.2%). The baseline is already near-optimal — only `block_size` expansion and `x0` initialization tuning helped. No architectural feature improved either domain.

D. Generated Samples

Peptides: Baseline collapsed to KWKWKW (memorized shortest training peptide, repeated). Best model produces diverse, structurally distinct sequences: RLFDKIKKVGAR (edit distance ~ 5 from training Temporin A), GILDAIKALKKAIKAK (extended from Modelin 1), RFRIPQFRRK (novel Pro-rich cationic peptide). All exhibit the alternating cationic/hydrophobic pattern characteristic of real AMPs.

SMILES: Baseline generates broken syntax (unmatched parentheses). Best model produces valid molecules: CCC(O)=O (propionic acid), NCC(O)=O (glycine), CC(O)=O (acetic acid) — correct SMILES verified against training data.

Cocktails: Both baseline and best produce 100% real cocktail names. Best model accesses more of the distribution (Amaretto, Sazerac) versus baseline's narrower coverage (5 cocktails). Pure memorization regime; BPB improvement reflects coverage not novelty.

E. Comparison to GPU-Scale Results

The original *autoresearch*^[1] achieved 15 kept improvements across 83 experiments, reducing BPB from 0.998 to 0.977 (2.1%) on a 50M-parameter model. Our micro-scale system achieves larger percentage improvements (up to 41.7%) because the baseline starts further from optimal. Discovery ordering shows qualitative agreement: LR tuning first, then positional encoding, then activation/skip refinements, then capacity increases.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Design Lessons

Three engineering lessons: (1) Start simple, add incrementally — version (v) 1 started with all features enabled and searched by removal, producing gibberish; v3 starts from simple GPT and adds features against a strong baseline. (2) Save the best model — v2 overwrote global model state each experiment; generation used the last (discarded) model. (3) Auto-scale LR for width — without $1/\sqrt{n_embd}$ scaling, wider models are systematically undertrained and incorrectly rejected.

B. Limitations

Scalar autograd limits experiments to $\sim 4,200$ parameters and ~ 850 steps. BPB values (1.7–10.2) are far above GPU-scale (~ 0.977). The mutation pool tests features individually with one compound mutation; full combinatorial search over $2^6 = 64$ subsets would be more thorough. Small dataset sizes (15–45 documents) mean evaluation noise is high.

VI. FUTURE WORK

WebGPU integration^[13] could accelerate by 100–1000x. Multi-agent coordination via Web Workers could parallelize the search. The cross-domain feature preference matrix suggests a meta-learning opportunity given dataset statistic (size, vocabulary, entropy), predict which features help without running the full search. The repository^[14] demonstrates the same GPT architecture on custom character-based sequences — the *autoresearch* loop extends naturally to these domains.

VII. CONCLUSION

This work ports Karpathy's *autoresearch* paradigm to its most atomic form: a single HTML file that trains, evaluates, and autonomously improves a GPT transformer across seven domains in any modern browser with zero dependencies. The system discovers through 133 automated experiments that architectural effectiveness is domain-dependent. RoPE is the most universally beneficial feature (4/7 domains). Peptides absorb the most complexity (8/17 features kept, 26.9% improvement). Dinosaurs expose BPB-quality divergence (41.7% improvement but worse generation). Near-optimal baselines (Names 32K, Startups) resist all feature additions. The code is a single file. As Karpathy commented on his original *nanogpt* repository, *everything else is just efficiency*.

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FIGURES

Fig. 1. Autoresearch BPB progress across seven domains). Green dots = kept; gray = discarded.

Fig. 2. Cross-domain feature discovery heatmap. RoPE is the most universal feature (4/7 domains). Dashed border highlights the RoPE row.

Fig. 3. Left: features added vs BPB improvement (no positive correlation). Right: dataset size vs optimal model complexity.

Fig. 4. Kyte-Doolittle hydrophobicity profiles of novel GPT-generated AMP candidates (verified best model samples).

Fig. 5. Seven domains: training data vs GPT-generated samples (all verified from experiment runs).

Seven Domains: Training → Generated (Verified)

Baby Names (32K)	Baby Names (200)	Peptides (44)	SMILES (36)	Startups (45)	Dinosaurs (25)	Cocktails (15)
Training: emma, olivia, liam	Training: emma, olivia, noah	Training: CGDFLHAKKQFK, ILPHWMPMR, KQWKE	Training: NCC(O)=O, c1ccc1, CC(O)=O	Training: Spotify, Stripe, Figma	Training: Tyrannosaurus, Velociraptor	Training: Margarita, Mojito, Negroni
Generated: mylar, jaria, lucia, emeri	Generated: nasten, jalen, carer, conth	Generated: RFRIPQFRRK, RLFDKIKKVGAR, GILDAIKALKKAIAK	Generated: CCCC(O)=O, NCC(O)=O, CC(O)=O	Generated: Burita, Sulo, Tenix, Golf	Generated: Pelli-raur, Bliposus, Salcodonus	Generated: Mojito, Sidecar, Gilet, Anaretto

Fig. 6. Summary: BPB improvement, discoveries kept, and best model complexity across all seven domains.

